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Viral Marketing: Word of Mouth To Word of Mouse Marketing Communication

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Abstract

Viral marketing is a technique of reaching customers through social media and other platforms on internet. It is like traditional word of mouth communication but assisted by internet. The use of internet makes it fast and if used properly may bring great profit with little or no expenses as most of the channels used in viral marketing are free and therefore good for those organizations which have very limited budget for promotion. The reason for great success of viral marketing is the change in customer buying behavior these days. Presently customers usually ignore the advertising message at traditional media due to its paid and hyper nature but they don't resist the message passed along by friends or other acquaintances on their social networks. The present study is theoretical and comprehensive study of viral marketing, its scope, principles, pros and cons.

Keywords: Internet ,Marketing, Messages, Promotion, Viral .

Introduction:

With the advent of internet, every sphere of life has witnessed sea changes and it has dramatically transformed the way of communication also. Today Whatsapp, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram have created their own social communities and provide users a platform to share their information and opinions. This is also offering the marketers a new avenue to reach its wide range of customers quickly, effectively and in more cost effective manner than traditional method. Customers are now aware enough and understand the gimmicks and tricks of marketers and they usually ignore the traditional advertising messages. The present study is theoretical and exploratory in nature.

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